

Unusual behaviour of dimethyl sulfoxide towards different alcohols in the presence of cyanuric chloride[†]

Subrata Kumar Chaudhuri^a, Amit Pramanik^b, Rimi Roy^c, Sagar Khan^c, Avishek Ghatak^c and Sanjay Bhar^{c*}

^aKhorop High School, Howrah, West Bengal, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Taki Government College, North 24-Parganas-743 429, West Bengal, India

^cDepartment of Chemistry, Organic Chemistry Section, Jadavpur University, Kolkata-700 032, India

E-mail : sanjaybharin@yahoo.com, sanjay_bhar@chemistry.jdvu.ac.in

Manuscript received 04 July 2013, accepted 05 July 2013

Abstract : Dimethyl sulfoxide in combination with cyanuric chloride in dichloromethane solvent behaved differently with alcohols having different structural features. The products were obtained as methylene acetal or methyl thioether or methyl enethioether depending on the substitution pattern of the alcohols. A plausible mechanism has been proposed on the basis of isotope labeling studies.

Keywords : Alcohols, cyanuric chloride, dimethyl sulfoxide, isotope labelling.

Introduction

Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) is not only used as a protic polar solvent but also acts as an oxidant in organic synthesis¹. Combinations of DMSO with electrophilic "activators" like trifluoroacetic anhydride, thionyl chloride, oxalyl chloride, *t*-butyl hypochlorite, acetic anhydride, acetyl chloride, *N*-halosuccinimides, methanesulfonyl chloride, dicyclohexylcarbodiimide, hydrobromic acid and hydrochloric acid are highly useful for the oxidation of alcohols to carbonyl compounds, in the synthesis of sulfimines, sulfoximines as well as in other synthetically important reactions^{2,3}.

In recent times, cyanuric chloride (2,4,6-trichloro-1,3,5-triazine, to be called TCT hereafter) has emerged as an efficient solid reagent for important organic transformations. It can be conveniently handled and it is relatively less toxic compared to many other reagents of similar kind. Over the last few years this reagent was utilized as an activator⁴ during the reduction of carboxylic acid to primary alcohol, as a chlorinating agent⁵ in the preparation of sulfonyl chlorides from sulfonic acids, as a cou-

pling agent⁶ during the synthesis of hydroxamic acids from carboxylic acids, as a catalyst for ammonium thiocyanate-mediated solvent-free conversion of thiiranes⁷ from oxiranes, as π -spacer⁸ during the synthesis and photovoltaic studies of donor- π -acceptor dyes, as a promoter⁹ for the labeling of mouse anti-quail IgY with horseradish peroxidase and as a catalyst¹⁰ for Pictet-Spengler reaction with electron-donating aldehydes. TCT in combination with DMF was used as a mild chlorinating agent for the conversion of alcohols and β -aminoalcohols to the corresponding alkyl chlorides¹¹, regioselective synthesis of unsymmetrical allyl chlorides through *ipso*- and *tele*-substitution¹² and construction¹³ of 2-azetidinone moieties. Oxidation of thiols to disulfides¹⁴ and deprotection of 1,3-dithioacetals and 1,3-oxathiolanes to the carbonyl compounds¹⁵ took place very efficiently under mild conditions using TCT in combination with DMSO. An efficient protocol for the oxidation of different alcohols to the corresponding carbonyl compounds was reported where DMSO in combination with TCT was used as the oxidant at low temperature in THF solvent¹⁶.

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

Results and discussion

In the course of our ongoing research programme, we attempted the oxidation of a few primary and secondary alcohols following the reported procedure¹⁶ using DMSO in combination with TCT where dichloromethane was used as a solvent instead of THF. Surprisingly, we did not get the corresponding carbonyl compounds as the products. Rather, the alcohols were converted to the corresponding methylene acetals, even in the absence of triethylamine (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Formation of methylene acetal from alcohol.

We undertook an investigation to exploit the synthetic potential of the aforesaid reaction along with mechanistic

studies. In a typical general procedure, cyanuric chloride was added to anhydrous DMSO with stirring when a white precipitate was obtained (TCT-DMSO). Structurally different alcohols dissolved in anhydrous dichloromethane were added dropwise to this precipitate. After stirring for two hours the reactions were complete and the products were isolated by usual work-up with diethyl ether. Interestingly, different products were obtained from alcohols differing in their substitution patterns. Detailed results have been presented in Table 1.

As evident from Table 1, aliphatic, benzylic and alicyclic alcohols were smoothly converted to the corresponding methylene acetals (dialkoxymethanes) in good yield (entries 1–4). Interestingly, diaryl carbinol produced diarylthiomethylmethane (entry 5). Cinnamyl alcohol afforded the corresponding methylene acetal along with the bis-ether in 6 : 1 ratio (determined by ¹H NMR) (entry 6). It is extremely important to note that diaryl alkyl carbinol (tertiary alcohol) afforded diaryl ene-thioether instead of any of the aforesaid compounds (entry 7). There

Table 1. Reaction of different alcohols with DMSO in the presence of cyanuric chloride

Entry	Substrate	Product(s)	Yield (%)
1			68 ¹⁷
2			85 ¹⁸
3			65 ¹⁸
4			80 ^{19,20}
5			70 ²¹

6			78
		+	
			(6 ²² : 1 ²³) ^b
7 ^c			65 ²⁴
8		No reaction	---
9			82
10			75

^aReaction time 2 h, yields refer to those of isolated pure products, characterized spectroscopically.

^bDetermined by ¹H NMR (300 MHz).

^cTriethylamine (3 molar equivalents) was added after the substrate.

was no reaction when there was methoxycarbonyl (-COOMe) moiety in place of methyl group in the previous alcohol, the substrate was recovered unaffected (entry 8). Aryl substituted 1,4-diols on similar treatment furnished novel seven membered 1,3-dioxygenated heterocyclic skeleton (entries 9 and 10). Although benzyl alcohol exclusively produced the corresponding methylene acetal without a trace of benzaldehyde, 4-methoxybenzyl alcohol on similar treatment furnished the corresponding methylene acetal along with *p*-anisaldehyde in the ratio of 4 : 1 (determined by ¹H NMR). Dialkoxymethanes and their derivatives are extensively used as the intermediates in the synthesis of plasticizers, monomers for cross-linking agents and in the synthesis of various biologically

important compounds, some of which show antiviral and antimicrobial activity²². Aryl substituted ene-thioethers with potential pharmacological activities²⁵ which are otherwise difficult to prepare can also be obtained through the aforesaid reaction. The same methodology can also be utilized for the construction of novel [1,3]-dioxepane²⁶ skeletons from easily accessible 1,4-diols.

From the results obtained so far it is clear that the outcome of the said reaction depends critically on the nature of the substituents. These interesting findings prompted us to investigate the mechanistic pathway of this unprecedented chemical transformation. It was initially thought that the -CH₂- moiety of the methylene acetal might be incorporated from dichloromethane used

as a solvent. When benzyl alcohol was treated with TCT-DMSO in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, diethyl ether and tetrahydrofuran in place of dichloromethane, the desired product dibenzylloxymethane was obtained preponderantly along with some unidentified by-products in varying amounts (in case of diethyl ether, formation of by-product was minimum among all the aforesaid solvents). Therefore, it can be concluded that $-\text{CH}_2-$ moiety in the product was not incorporated from CH_2Cl_2 .

Then it was speculated that the methylene ($-\text{CH}_2-$) moiety might be derived from the methyl group of DMSO¹⁹. To prove this, benzyl alcohol, 1-phenylbutane-1,4-diol and 1,1-diphenylethanol were reacted individually with TCT in the presence of DMSO- d_6 in place of DMSO using CH_2Cl_2 as solvent (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2. Isotope labeling studies.

For benzyl alcohol, the singlet at δ 4.64 (due to $-\text{OCH}_2\text{Ph}$) in the ^1H NMR spectrum appeared at δ 4.65 in the deuterated product but the singlet at δ 4.87 (due to $-\text{OCH}_2\text{O}-$) was absent. Similarly in the ^{13}C NMR spectrum, the peak at δ 69.7 (due to $-\text{OCH}_2\text{Ph}$) appeared at δ 69.4 in the deuterated product but there was no peak at δ 94.2 (due to $-\text{OCH}_2\text{O}-$). The AB quartet at δ 4.92 (due to $-\text{OCH}_2\text{O}-$) in the ^1H NMR of 4-phenyl-[1,3]-dioxepane vanished in the deuterated analogue. In ^{13}C NMR, the peak at δ 94.0 was absent in the deuterated product. The singlet at δ 2.43 (due to $-\text{SCH}_3$) in the ^1H NMR and the

signal at δ 18.0 (due to $-\text{SCH}_3$) in the ^{13}C NMR of the ene thioether disappeared in the deuterated product. These results conclusively proved that the incorporated $-\text{CH}_2-$ and $-\text{SCH}_3$ moieties (as the case might be) were derived from DMSO. On the basis of the aforesaid observations a plausible mechanistic pathway has been proposed in Fig. 1 to rationalize the results.

As shown in Fig. 1, one of three chlorine atoms in TCT underwent nucleophilic substitution through the electron-rich oxygen atom of DMSO analogous to an earlier report¹¹ with DMF. This adduct was obtained as a white precipitate generating a sulfonium ion intermediate **A**. Intramolecular deprotonation of the CH_3 -group in the sulfonium ion moiety of **A** took place by the neighbouring basic nitrogen through an entropically favoured six-mem-

bered cyclic transition state to furnish a sulphur ylide **B**, which underwent facile elimination (due to high nucleofugality of the triazine moiety **C**) to generate sulfinium cation **D**. Formation of **D** had the literature precedence²⁷ in similar type of transformation during the synthesis of Tröger's base where DMSO/HCl was utilized as formaldehyde equivalent. This highly reactive electron-deficient sulfinium cation **D** acted as an electrophile where it underwent nucleophilic attack by the alcohol **E** present in the system. Concomitant elimination of methanethiol (CH_3SH) via intramolecular

Fig. 1. Plausible mechanistic pathway.

prototropic shift led to oxonium ion intermediate **F** which provided the formyl cation equivalent. **F** underwent further transformation depending on the structure and substituents in the alcohol. In case of unhindered alcohols, a second alcohol molecule attacks (PATH A) as nucleophilic

generating the methylene acetal **G** (entries 1 to 4 in Table 1). In case of diaryl secondary alcohol, elimination of formaldehyde as a neutral molecule yielded stabilized diarylmethyl carbocation **H** which underwent subsequent nucleophilic attack by methanethiol (generated *in situ* from

DMSO during the conversion of **E** to **F**) producing thioether **I** (entry 5 in Table 1), as shown in PATH B. In case of cinnamyl alcohol, the corresponding carbocation was stabilized by extended conjugation. As the electrophilic carbocationic centre was sterically more accessible, so another alcohol molecule instead of methanethiol acted as nucleophile (PATH C) giving bis-ether **J** as a minor product along with the usual methylene acetal (entry 6 in Table 1). For 1,4-diol, proximity-driven entropically favoured intramolecular attack by the 2° -OH on the electrophilic formyl carbon equivalent led to the formation of 7-membered dioxigenated heterocyclic backbone of [1,3]-dioxepane (entries 9 and 10 in Table 1). In case of diaryl alkyl carbinol (entry 7 in Table 1), PATH D was followed. The analogous carbocation **K** (obtained by the loss of HCHO) was deprotonated with triethylamine to generate 1,1-diphenylethene **L**. It was attacked with methanethiol (generated *in situ* from DMSO) at the less substituted carbon of the double bond to produce **M** where the incipient negative charge was mesomerically stabilized by two phenyl rings. The ene thioether **N** was obtained through hydride shift (analogous to cross-Cannizzaro reaction) from **M** to formaldehyde (generated *in situ* from DMSO during the conversion of **F** to **H**). Formation of methanethiol from DMSO was conclusively proved by studying the reaction with DMSO- d_6 where SCD_3 was incorporated in place of SCH_3 in the final product (Scheme 2). In the case of alcohols bearing electron withdrawing substituent (e.g. COOMe) (entry 8 in Table 1), the substrate was recovered unaffected. Formation of electron-deficient intermediate was not feasible due to their destabilization by the methoxycarbonyl group. So there was no further transformation.

Conclusion

The present investigation developed a novel protocol with multifarious applications. Primary and many secondary alcohols were converted to the corresponding methylene acetals with potential synthetic applications. Diaryl secondary carbinols were converted to thioether whereas diaryl alkyl tertiary carbinol accomplished ene thioether. Isotope-labeling studies established the mechanistic pathways to rationalize the formation of different products depending on the nature of the substituents in the substrates. This reaction can be utilized for the preparation of some deuterated compounds of synthetic and

mechanistic importance. Moreover, the aforesaid results advise a caution while using TCT as an activator of DMSO for oxidative transformations of alcohols.

Experimental

General procedure for the reaction of alcohols with cyanuric chloride (TCT) in presence of DMSO :

Representative procedure for bis-(benzyloxy)methane (entry 2 in Table 1) :

Cyanuric chloride (405 mg, 2.2 mmol) was added in small portions to dry DMSO (1.2 ml, 16.8 mmol) with constant stirring at around 10 °C. The solution became turbid and within 15 min a white precipitate was obtained. To that precipitate freshly distilled benzyl alcohol (216 mg, 2 mmol) in dry dichloromethane (2.5 ml) was added slowly with stirring. Stirring was continued for another 2 h at room temperature (monitored by TLC) and then diethyl ether (5 ml) was added to the reaction mixture. The ether extract was transferred to a separatory funnel and the residue was washed thoroughly with ether (2 × 10 ml). The combined organic extracts were washed with water (2 × 10 ml), followed by saturated potassium carbonate solution (2 × 10 ml) and finally with distilled water (3 × 15 ml), dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent was evaporated to yield the product which was further purified by column chromatography over silica gel (2% ethyl acetate-hexane) to furnish pure bis-(benzyloxy)methane¹⁸ (180 mg, 85%) as colourless liquid (sublimed at 140–142 °C under 2 mm of Hg pressure); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 4.64 (4H, s), 4.87 (2H, s), 7.27–7.35 (10H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 69.7, 94.2, 127.9, 128.2, 128.7, 137.9.

The deuterated product (Scheme 2) was prepared in a similar way by treating benzyl alcohol (54 mg, 0.5 mmol) with TCT (120 mg, 0.65 mmol) in presence of DMSO- d_6 (0.4 ml, 5.6 mmol) for 2 h and purified by column chromatography (2% ethyl acetate-hexane) over silica gel.

Spectral data of the deuterated product : ¹H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 4.65 (4H, s), 7.25–7.35 (10H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 69.4, 127.6, 127.9, 128.4, 137.8.

Reaction of cinnamyl alcohol with TCT-DMSO (entry 6 in Table 1) :

Freshly distilled cinnamyl alcohol (270 mg, 2 mmol)

was treated similarly at room temperature with TCT (405 mg, 2.2 mmol) and DMSO (1.2 ml) for about 4 h. The crude product (226 mg) furnished two spots in TLC. These were separated by column chromatography over silica gel using 5% ethyl acetate-hexane mixture. The first fraction (minor) was identified as bis(3-phenylprop-2-enyl)-ether (28 mg, 11%) (entry 6 in Table 1), the second fraction (major) being the expected bis(3-phenylprop-2-enyloxy)methane (191 mg, 68%) (entry 6 in Table 1). The low yield of the products was attributed to the loss of material during column chromatography.

Spectral and physical data :

*bis(3-Phenylprop-2-enyl) ether*²³ :

Viscous liquid, purified further by column filtration on silica gel using 2% ethyl acetate-hexane as eluent; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 4.24 (4H, distorted doublet, *J* 7.4 Hz), 6.32 (2H, td, *J*₁ 15.6, *J*₂ 7.1 Hz), 6.66 (2H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz), 7.25–7.41 (10H, m).

*bis(3-Phenylprop-2-enyloxy)methane*²² :

Colourless liquid; b.p. 214–216 °C at 1 mm of Hg; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 4.27 (4H, d, *J* 6.1 Hz), 4.81 (2H, s), 6.30 (2H, td, *J*₁ 15.8, *J*₂ 6.0 Hz), 6.63 (2H, d, *J* 15.9 Hz), 7.19–7.45 (10H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 68.2, 93.7, 125.5, 126.5, 127.7, 128.5, 132.6, 136.6.

Reaction of 1,1-diphenyl ethanol with TCT-DMSO (entry 7 in Table 1) :

The procedure for this reaction was same except that Et₃N (0.8 ml, 6 mmol) was added after 15 min from the addition of 1,1-diphenyl ethanol (395 mg, 2 mmol) in dichloromethane (2.5 ml) to the precipitate formed from TCT (405 mg, 2.2 mmol) and dry DMSO (1.2 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for about 3.5 h. The crude product was purified by column chromatography over silica gel (5% ethyl acetate-hexane) to furnish the product 1-(methylthio)-2,2-diphenylethene²⁴ as dense liquid which solidified on standing. This was further purified by recrystallization from hexane (m.p. 70–71 °C; yield 295 mg, 65%); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.43 (3H, s), 6.52 (1H, s), 7.15–7.38 (10H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 18.0, 126.9, 127.0, 127.5, 127.7, 128.3, 129.7, 138.3, 139.5, 141.7.

Spectral data of the deuterated product (-SCD₃ analogue) (61% yield) : ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 6.54 (1H, s), 7.19–7.43 (10H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 126.8, 127.0, 127.5, 128.0, 128.2, 128.3, 129.7, 138.4, 139.5, 141.7.

The spectral, analytical and physical data for the other compounds corresponding to Table 1 are given below for ready reference.

*Diheptyloxymethane (heptyl formal)*¹⁷ (entry 1 in Table 1) :

Colourless oil, purified by column chromatography on silica gel using 2% ethyl acetate-hexane as eluent; yield 68%, b.p. 122–123 °C at 2 mm of Hg; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 0.84–0.92 (6H, m), 1.18–1.34 (16H, m), 1.53–1.62 (4H, m), 3.52 (4H, t, *J* 6.6 Hz), 4.66 (2H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 14.1, 22.7, 26.3, 29.2, 29.9, 31.9, 68.0, 95.3.

*bis-[2-(1,3-Diphenyl)propyloxy]methane*¹⁸ (entry 3 in Table 1) :

Colourless viscous liquid, purified by column chromatography over silica gel using 5% ethyl acetate-hexane as eluent; sublimed at 130 °C under 0.3 mm of Hg pressure, yield 65%; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.55–2.69 (8H, m), 3.88–3.94 (2H, m), 4.46 (2H, s), 7.07–7.27 (20H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 40.6, 78.8, 92.6, 126.6, 128.6, 130.0, 139.0.

Dicyclohexyloxymethane^{19,20} (entry 4 in Table 1) : Colourless oil, purified by column chromatography through a silica gel column using 5% ethyl acetate-hexane as eluent; yield 80%, b.p. 110–112 °C at 1 mm Hg; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.10–1.26 (8H, m), 1.47–1.50 (4H, m), 1.67–1.68 (4H, m), 1.85–1.88 (4H, m), 3.47–3.58 (2H, m), 4.71 (2H, s).

*Diphenylthiomethylmethane*²¹ (entry 5 in Table 1) : Light yellow oily liquid, purified by column chromatography on silica gel using 5% ethyl acetate-hexane as eluent; yield 70%; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.97 (3H, s), 5.04 (1H, s), 7.23 (2H, d, *J* 6.3 Hz), 7.31 (4H, t, *J* 6.1 Hz), 7.41 (4H, d, *J* 6.9 Hz).

4-Phenyl-1,3-dioxepane (entry 9 in Table 1) :

Low melting solid (m.p. 62–64 °C), purified by filtration chromatography on a short column of silica gel using 5% ethyl acetate-hexane; yield 82%; ¹H NMR (300

MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.77–2.06 (4H, m), 3.77–3.85, 3.93–3.99 (2H, m), 4.74 (1H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz), 4.92 (2H, AB quartet, *J* 5.4 Hz), 7.22–7.35 (5H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 29.4, 37.4, 67.4, 79.6, 94.0, 126.2, 127.7, 128.7, 143.7. Anal. Calcd. for C₁₁H₁₄O₂ : C, 74.12; H, 7.91. Found : C, 74.04; H, 7.82; HRMS Calcd. for C₁₁H₁₄O₂ + Na⁺ : 201.2120, Found : 201.2129.

Spectral data of the deuterated product (-OCD₂O-analogue) (yield 78%) :

¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.76–2.05 (4H, m), 3.76–3.84, 3.92–3.99 (2H, m), 4.73 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz), 7.23–7.34 (5H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 28.8, 36.9, 66.9, 79.1, 125.6, 127.4, 128.2, 143.2.

4-p-Tolyl-1,3-dioxepane (entry 10 in Table 1) :

Semi-solid mass, purified by column filtration on a short-plug of silica gel using 5% ethyl acetate-hexane, followed by sublimation at 130 °C under 0.3 mm of Hg pressure; yield 75%, ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.74–2.03 (4H, m), 2.32 (3H, s), 3.76–3.98 (2H, m), 4.70 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 4.91 (2H, AB quartet, *J* 5.4 Hz), 7.13–7.25 (4H, m); Anal. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₆O₂ : C, 74.96; H, 8.38. Found : C, 74.78; H, 8.46.

Acknowledgement

Authors express sincere gratitude to Mr. J. Poddar of Jadavpur University and Mr. N. Dutta of Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science for necessary assistance. The aforesaid investigation has enjoyed financial support from DST-PURSE-programme at Jadavpur University and the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, Government of India (CSIR Grant No.01(2383)/10/EMR-II) which are also gratefully acknowledged. RR and AG thank CSIR, New Delhi, Government of India for Senior Research Fellowship and Junior Research Fellowship, respectively. SK thanks UGC, New Delhi, Government of India for Senior Research Fellowship.

References

1. C. Li, Y. Xu, M. Lu, Z. Zhao, L. Liu, Z. Zhao, Y. Cui, P. Zheng, X. Ji and G. Gas, *Synlett.*, 2002, 2041.
2. K. Omura and D. Swern, *Tetrahedron*, 1978, **34**, 1651.
3. A. J. Mancuso and D. Swern, *Synthesis*, 1981, 165.
4. M. Falorni, A. Porcheddu and M. Taddei, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1999, **40**, 4395.
5. G. Blotny, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2003, **44**, 1499.
6. G. Giacomelli, A. Porcheddu and M. Salaris, *Org. Lett.*, 2003, **5**, 2715.
7. B. P. Bandgar, N. S. Joshi and V. T. Kamble, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2006, **47**, 4775.
8. J. Liu, K. Wanga, F. Xu, Z. Tang, W. Zheng, J. Zhang, C. Li, T. Yu and X. You, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2011, **52**, 6492.
9. N. Kassim, A. B. Mtenga, W.-B. Shim and D.-H. Chung, *J. Microbiol. Biotech.*, 2013, **23**, 527.
10. A. Sharma, M. Singh, N. N. Rai and D. Sawant, *Beilstein J. Org. Chem.*, 2013, **9**, 1235.
11. L. D. Luca, G. Giacomelli and A. Porcheddu, *Org. Lett.*, 2002, **4**, 553.
12. S. Roy, T. Das, M. Saha, S. K. Chaudhuri and S. Bhar, *Synth. Commun.*, 2007, **37**, 4367.
13. M. Zarei and A. Jarrahpour, *Synlett.*, 2011, 2572.
14. B. Karimi, H. Hazarkhani and D. Zareyee, *Synthesis*, 2002, 2513.
15. B. Karimi and H. Hazarkhani, *Synthesis*, 2003, 2547.
16. L. D. Luca, G. Giacomelli and A. Porcheddu, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2001, **66**, 7907.
17. J. H. Wotiz and J. A. Webster, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, **21**, 1536.
18. A. Cornelis and P. Laszlo, *Synthesis*, 1982, 162.
19. S. Hanessian, G. Yang-Chung, P. Lavallee and A. G. Pernet, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 8929.
20. A. R. A. S. Deshmuch, V. K. Gumaste and B. M. Bhawal, *Synth. Commun.*, 1995, **25**, 3939.
21. H. Ikehira, S. Tanimoto, T. Oida and M. Okano, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1983, **48**, 1120.
22. M. G. Kulkarni, S. I. Davawala, A. K. Doke and A. V. Doke, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2003, **42**, 2121.
23. Y. Kayaki, T. Koda and T. Ikariya, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2004, **69**, 2595.
24. G. A. Russel and L. A. Ochrymowycz, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1970, **35**, 764.
25. D. Alves, F. Schumacher, R. Brandao, C. W. Nogueira and G. Zeni, *Synlett.*, 2006, 1035.
26. L.-X. Shao, B. Xu, J.-W. Huang and M. Shi, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2006, **12**, 510.
27. Z. Li, X. Xu, Y. Peng, Z. Jiang, C. Ding and X. Qian, *Synthesis*, 2005, 1228.